

Formulation and Evolution of Polyherbal Powder Use to Treat Hemorrhoids

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ABSTRACT: -

Hemorrhoids Also Known As Piles It Is A Common Medical Condition Characterized By Swellon And Inflamed Veins In The Rectum And Anus. They Often Cause Discomfort, Pain, Itching And Bleeding. The Traditional Herbal Medicine Offers Various Polyherbal Formulation That Have Been Used. Polyherbal Formulation Are A Collection Of Therapeutics Entities That Are Formulated And Prepared On Basis Of The Healing Properties Of Individual Ingredients Such As Coconut Husk (*Cocos Nucifera*, Family:-*Arecaceae*), Amla (*Phyllanthus Emblica L.* Family:-*Phyllanthaceae*), Haldi (*Curcuma Longa*, Family:-*Zingiberaceae*), Methi (*Trigonella Foenum Gracum*, Family:-*Fabaceae*) To Treat Hemorrhoids. These Formulation Typically Consist Of A Blend Of Natural Ingredients Such As Herbs, Roots And Plant Extracts Known For Their Anti-Inflammatory, Analgesic And Vasoconstrictive Properties. This Formulation Of Polyherbal Powder Which Is Used Externally To Treatment Of External Hemorrhoids.

Key Words:- Hemorrhoids, Piles, Coconut Fibers, Polyherbal formulation, Anti-inflammatory.

INTRODUCTION:-

The Word Hemorrhoid Is Derived From The Greek Adjective Hemorrhoids, Which Means Bleeding (Haima =Blood; Rhoos= Flowing).The Word Pile Is Derived From The Latin Word Pila, Meaning A Ball. (1)Hemorrhoids Or Piles Are Common Ailment Among Adults. More Than Half Of Men And Women Aged 50 Year And Older Will Develop Hemorrhoids Symptoms During Their Lifetime.(2).In This Research Article We Will Formulate The Powder Dosage Form Which Can Be Use To Treatment Of External Hemorrhoids.there are two types of hemorrhoids External Hemorrhoids and Internal Hemorrhoids.External Hemorrhoids Are Swollen Veins Around The Skin Of The Anus. They Can Cause Itching, Pain, And Bleeding. Sometimes The Bleeding Can Lead To The Formation Of Blood Clots.Internal Hemorrhoids Are Swollen Veins Located Inside The Anus. You Cannot See Or Feel Them, And They Are Usually Painless. You Can Experience Painless Bleeding And See Blood In Your Stools Or On The Toilet Paper. Internal Hemorrhoids Can Become Painful If They Prolapse; In Such Cases, Hemorrhoid Protrudes From The Rectum. They Can Be Pushed Back Inside Gently To Avoid pain and Irritation.(3)

TYPES OF HEMORRHOIDS

Internal hemorrhoids

External hemorrhoids

Fig.1 'Internal Hemorrhoids And 'External Hemorrhoids. (4)

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MATERIAL AND METHODOLOGY:-

Preparation of Formulation Made Up Of Herbs

The Ingredients Were Individually Reduced To Fine Particles And Sieved (60mesh) To Obtain Respective Fine Powders. Powder Each Ingredients Was Weighed Separately And Thoroughly Mixed Together. The Composite Mixture Was Again Sieved (60mesh) To Obtain A Fine Powder Of The Finished Product.

Fig.2 Hemorrhoids Powder Formulation

Organoleptic Evaluation

Observe The Color, Texture And Visible Particle of the drug .

Pharmaceutical Evaluation

Pharmaceutical Parameter Like Bulk Density, Tapped Density, Hausner's Ratio, Carr's Index And Angle Of Repose Were Determined As Per Standard Protocols.

PREFORMULATION STUDY OF INGREDIENTS:-

[1]COCONUT HUSK

Biological Source = Cocos Nucifera (L.)

Family = Arecaceae

Chemical Constituent = Lignin, Cellulose, Hemicellulose, Pectin.

Bulk Density = Weight Of Powder/Bulk Volume Of Powder

$$= 20/35.5$$

$$=0.5$$

Tapped Density = Weight Of Powder/Tapped Volume Of Powder

$$=20/23.2$$

$$=0.8$$

Hauser's Ratio = Tapped Density/Bulk Density

$$=0.8/0.5$$

$$=1.6$$

Carr's Index = Tapped Density – Bulk Density/Tapped Density×100

$$=0.8-0.5/0.8\times 100$$

$$=37.5\%$$

Angle Of Repose Θ = $\tan^{-1}(H/R)$

$$= \tan^{-1}(2.4/5.45)$$

$$= \tan^{-1}(0.440)$$

$$=23.75$$

[2]HALDI

Biological Source = Curcuma Longa

Family = Zingiberaceae

Chemical Constituent = Demethoxy, Curcumin, Bisdemethoxy Curcumin, Zingiberene, Curcamol, Curcumenol, Eugenol.

Bulk Density = Weight Of Powder/Bulk Volume Of Powder

$$=20/23$$

$$=0.86$$

Tapped Density = Weight Of Powder/Tapped Volume Of Powder

$$=20/14.2$$

$$=1.40$$

Hauser's Ratio = Tapped Density/Bulk Density

$$= 1.40/0.86$$

$$=1.62$$

Carr's Index = Tapped Density – Bulk Density/Tapped Density×100

$$=1.40-0.86/1.40\times 100$$

$$=38\%$$

Angle Of Repose Θ = $\tan^{-1}(h/r)$

$$= \tan^{-1}(1.9/3.6)$$

$$= \tan^{-1}(0.52)$$

$$=26.5$$

[3]AMLA**Biological Source** = Phyllanthus Emblica L.**Family** = Euphorbiaceae**Chemical Constituent** = Tanins, Phyllembelin-Gallic Acid Ellagic Acid, Glucose Pectine, Vitamin-C.**Bulk Density**=Weight Of Powder/Bulk Volume Of Powder

$$=20/18.7$$

$$=1.06$$

Tapped Density=Weight Of Powder/Tapped Volume Of Powder

$$=20/13.3$$

$$1.50$$

Hauser's Ratio=Tapped Density/Bulk Density

$$=1.50/1.06$$

$$=1.41$$

Carr's Index=Tapped Density – Bulk Density/Tapped Density×100

$$=1.50-1.06/1.50\times 100$$

$$=29.33\%$$

Angle Of Repose Θ = $\tan^{-1}(h/r)$

$$=\tan^{-1}(2/3.55)$$

$$=\tan^{-1}(0.5)$$

$$=26.55$$

[4] METHI**Biological Source** = Trigonella Foenum Gracum**Family** = Fabaceae**Chemical Constituent**= Carbohydrate, Proteins Lipids, Alkaloids, Flavanoids, Fibers, Vitamins.**Bulk Density**=Weight Of Powder/Bulk Volume Of Powder

$$=20/14$$

$$=1.42$$

Tapped Density= Weight Of Powder/Tapped Volume Of Powder

$$=20/9$$

$$=2.22$$

Hauser's Ratio=Tapped Density/Bulk Density

$$=2.2/1.4$$

$$1.57$$

Carr's Index=Tapped Density – Bulk Density/Tapped Density×100

$$=2.22-1.42/2.22\times 100$$

$$=36\%$$

Angle Of Repose θ =tan-1(h/r)

$$=\tan^{-1}(2.5/4.3)$$

$$=\tan^{-1}(0.58)$$

$$=25.61$$

BATCH OPTIMIZATION PROCESS:-

COMPOSITION	BULK DENSITY	TAPPED DENSITY	HAUSNER RATIO	CARR'S INDEX	ANGLE OF REPOSE
BATCH-A Coconut Husk 5gm Haldi 4gm Amla 3gm Methi 2gm Starch 1gm Talc 1gm	0.44	0.61	1.38	27.8%	32.02
BATCH-B Coconut Husk 2gm Haldi 3gm Amla 4gm Methi 5gm Starch 1gm Talc 1gm	0.51	0.66	1.29	22.7%	25.64
BATCH-C Coconut Husk 4gm Methi 3gm Haldi 5gm Amla 2gm Starch 1gm Talc 1gm	0.48	0.69	1.43	30.4%	33.02

Fig.3

Hemorrhoids Powder Formulations

OPTIMIZED FORMULATION:-

INGREDIENTS	BIOLOGICAL SOURCE	QUANTITY
Coconut Husk (Burn The Shell Along With The Fibers, Which Convert Into Ash And Passed To Seive No 60, Coconut Husk Obtained In Powder Form)	Cocos Nucifera	2gm
Haldi	Curcuma longa	3gm
Amla	Phyllanthus Emblica L.	4gm
Methi	Trigonella Foenum	5gm
Starch	-	1gm
Talc	-	1gm

POST FORMULATION STUDIES OPTIMIZATION :-

Fig.4 Powder Sample

Fig.5 Bulk Density

Fig.6 Tapped Density

Fig.7 Angle of Repose

Fig.8 pH (6.7) of Powder Sample

FORMULATION OF THE HEMORRHOIDS POWDER:-

- All The Ingredients Taken And Reduced To Fine Powder Pass From The Sieve No 60.
- Again Mix All The Powder And Pass Sieved No 60
- Fine Powder Are Obtain Store The Powder In An Airtight Container.

Fig.8 Hemetreat Powder

RESULT:-

Prepared And Tested Polyherbal Hemorrhoids Powder Can Be Use To Treat External Hemorrhoids.

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